

Sustainability, innovation and export: Evidence from French SMEs in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region

Emilie Djivélékian

School of Economics, Shanghai University

No. 99 Shangda Road, BaoShan District, Shanghai 200444, China

Tel: +33 7 66 63 23 55 E-mail: djivelekian.emilie@gmail.com

Abstract

In light of the escalating economic influence of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), the intricate interplay of sustainability, innovation, and export performance assumes paramount significance. This study focuses on French SMEs in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (ARA) region, exploring the relatively uncharted territory of a synergistic approach to sustainability and innovation. Through a 2022-2023 field survey of 290 SMEs, employing Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Two-Stage Least Squares (2SLS) regression models, the research investigates the potential enhancement of export performance through this synergistic approach. The study reveals a positive impact, emphasizing the significance of sustainability certifications (EUR 24,416 additional export turnover per certification), R&D investment (EUR 1.38 boost per euro invested), and environmental patents (EUR 64,439 per patent). Qualitative insights enrich the understanding of challenges and opportunities, especially in terms of environmental footprint reduction. The findings underscore the need for prioritizing sustainability and innovation by French SMEs to thrive in export markets, with implications for policymakers in designing initiatives. In conclusion, this research offers a comprehensive framework for understanding the dynamics between sustainability, innovation, and export performance, providing practical guidance for SMEs and a methodological foundation for future regional research.

Keywords: SMEs, Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, export, innovation, sustainability

Publication date: December 4th, 2023

1. Introduction

In the constantly evolving global trade landscape, the role of SMEs is pivotal for economic efficiency and sustainable development. These enterprises, often operating in complex and uncharted territories, must navigate the intersection of sustainability and innovation to remain competitive.

1.1 The significance of SMEs in a globalized economy

In today's globalized economy, innovation and exports play a crucial role in driving economic growth and promoting sustainable development. SMEs are the backbone of many economies, including France, and are increasingly recognized for their potential to contribute to sustainable development through innovation and exports. The challenge facing SMEs is how to balance the pursuit of growth and profitability with the need to address environmental and social concerns. Some proponents state that strong economic growth contributes to economic and social development, as well as poverty reduction. This growth depends, among other factors, on its ability to blend in with the global economy through trade and investment. Even if public authorities are the ones which decide on the action to be taken in the fields of trade and investment, it is indeed the companies that trade and invest. Enterprises are essential in international trade as they are the entities which include all the activities of a person or a group of people who work to provide goods or services to their clients. The goal of this exchange is to reach a financial equilibrium or surplus.

In market economies, the business sector is predominantly private, and it covers the whole range of economic activities which extends from agriculture to services. Trade is largely a part of these activities, via the

manufacturing industry, even if the sector tends more and more to widen its scope of action to the infrastructure sectors and social services. Within the private sector, there are different categories of actors intervening in the market: self-employed, micro-enterprises, small enterprises, medium-sized enterprises, large enterprises, and multinational companies. Private small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are an essential source of employment and generate considerable revenue both internally and for export within developed countries as well as in developing countries. Clearly, increasing the competitiveness of SMEs could contribute to economic and social development and poverty reduction.

1.2 The vital socio-economic role and export potential of SMEs in France

There is no universal definition of what is meant by “SMEs”, but most countries around the world agree that they play a vital role in economic prosperity. SMEs constitute a considerable part of the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of each country and employ a significant portion of the global workforce. Even though there is no precise data, according to World Bank research, SMEs represent nearly 90% of all businesses and more than 50% of employment worldwide. According to the INSEE, SMEs in France employ less than 250 employees with a turnover less than 50 million euros and balance sheet less than 43 million euros. In 2021, there are 4,352,610 of these companies in France (INSEE, 2023).

In the 2018 report "Enterprises in France" by the National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE), underscores the pervasive presence and substantial contributions of SMEs to the country's economic landscape (INSEE, 2018). SMEs, which encompass micro-enterprises, constitute an overwhelming 99.8% of all companies in France. These agile businesses collectively generate a turnover of 830 billion euros, representing 21% of the nation's total business turnover. In contrast, large corporations contribute 1,385 billion euros, equivalent to 35% of the total turnover. Moreover, when examining value creation, SMEs play a significant role, accounting for 22% of the total value added, amounting to 252 billion euros, while larger firms contribute 31%, with 352 billion euros in added value. In terms of employment, SMEs have a substantial impact, providing jobs for 3,670 million people, constituting 29% of the total employment in France. Large corporations, although influential, represent a slightly lower share, employing 3,354 individuals, which corresponds to 26% of the nation's total employment (INSEE, 2020).

Nevertheless, when it comes to exports, the dynamics shift. Large companies take the lead, contributing over half of France's total exports at 54%, amounting to 386 billion euros. In contrast, SMEs account for a smaller portion of French exports, representing only 12% with 85 billion euros in export value (INSEE, 2020), revealing the huge export potential that exists for French SMEs. Although the country currently has around 150,000 exporting SMEs, the government is aiming to increase this figure up to 200,000. Exporting is essential for stimulating the economy, creating jobs and increasing the competitiveness of French companies on the international stage. In this context, exporting is emerging as a key element in the growth and competitiveness of these SMEs. However, to remain competitive on international markets, they must constantly adapt to economic, social and environmental challenges.

1.3 Sustainability perspectives and innovation dynamics in the context of SMEs

Sustainability is defined as the "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs." (The World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). The World Economic Forum (WEF) insists that harnessing the power of SMEs is not only critical but also pivotal in shaping the future of sustainability. Since SMEs are integrated into corporate value chains, they can significantly influence the non-financial performance metrics of large corporations. Therefore, embracing sustainability as a catalyst for innovation, impact, and growth, rather than a mere compliance requirement, exemplifies the transformative potential of these smaller enterprises. The United Nations (UN) also insisted on the relevance, roles, and contributions of SMEs to the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It delves into how SMEs impact each of the SDGs by examining their role in various aspects, such as economic activity, job creation, income generation, particularly for marginalized communities, provision of essential services (e.g., education, healthcare, water, and sanitation), and their

influence as both energy users and environmental contributors (UN-DESA, 2020). This paradigm shift presents fresh business opportunities, not only for the broader private sector but also specifically for MSMEs, including in the French economy. According to the Business and Sustainable Development Commission (BSDC), embracing sustainable business models could unlock economic opportunities worth USD12 trillion and create 380 million jobs by 2030, with more than 50% of these opportunities located in developing countries. In 2014, it was estimated USD 1.2 trillion market potential for SMEs operating in the developing world within the "clean technology" sector, spanning the decade until 2023 (UNDESA, 2020). SMEs could even play a pivotal role in advancing the commercialization of low-cost sanitation technology from the Bill & Melinda Gate Foundation, projected to reach a global market value of USD 6 billion by 2030.

Innovation, whether technological, organizational or commercial, remains a powerful growth driver for SMEs. Indeed, innovation serves as the primary catalyst for enhancing productivity and income growth, which in turn plays a pivotal role in shaping the export performance of French SMEs (OECD, 2018). First and foremost, it enables SMEs to develop new and improved products or services that meet the specific needs of foreign markets. This ability to offer innovative solutions confers a significant competitive advantage, as it can lead to product differentiation and greater acceptance on international markets. It can also help to improve productivity. By developing new, more efficient technologies, processes or working methods, SMEs can reduce their production costs, thereby boosting their competitiveness on international markets. Improved productivity often translates into more competitive prices and greater profitability, which is essential for export success. However, it should be noted that innovation cannot be considered in isolation. It interacts with other key factors, such as institutional factors, governance, company resources and capabilities, and the business environment. For example, innovation-friendly regulations and supportive government policies can create an environment conducive to innovation and exporting. What's more, a synergistic approach to sustainability initiatives can also boost innovation. Sustainability practices, such as reducing carbon footprints, managing resources responsibly, and promoting social responsibility, can stimulate innovation by encouraging companies to rethink their processes and products to make them more sustainable. In this way, sustainable development and innovation are not necessarily in competition, but can be complementary, helping to improve the overall export performance of French SMEs.

2. Literature review

The existing body of literature has primarily examined the separate impacts of (i) innovation on export (Cassiman et al., 2010; Rennings & Rammer, 2010) or vice-versa (Aghion et al., 2018), (ii) sustainability on export or vice-versa (Arora & De, 2020), (iii) sustainability on innovation or vice-versa (Kuzma et al., 2020), but very few were able to study the three under a same research framework (Bos-Brouwers, 2009; Teplova et al., 2022; Villena-Manzanares & Souto-Pérez, 2016).

2.1 Influence of sustainability and innovation on SMEs export and value

According to Gaussens and Movahedi, innovation and exporting are two key elements in a country's economic development (Gaussens & Movahedi, 2016). They are often interdependent, creating a complex relationship that influences economic growth, global market competitiveness and long-term prosperity. The relationship between innovation and exports within the realm of SMEs is a highly significant subject in the contemporary scientific literature. The prevailing paradigm can be characterized as causal, as it proposes a cause-and-effect connection between innovation and exports (Love & Roper, 2015). In this paradigm, innovation is believed to have a positive influence on exports, and conversely, exports may have a positive impact on innovation. The findings of Golovko and Valentini indicate that Spanish manufacturing SMEs that simultaneously invest in innovation and exports experience superior growth compared to those who invest in either innovation or exports exclusively, or in neither (Golovko & Valentini, 2011). The return on investment for one activity rises with the performance level achieved in the other activity. However, Ayllón and Radicic discovered that while a complementarity between innovation and exports exists, it is primarily due to simultaneous effects (Ayllón & Radicic, 2019).

The concept of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) embodies a comprehensive framework designed for the evaluation of the ethical and sustainability practices embraced by corporations and institutions. In a study conducted by Teplova et al. regarding the sustainability determinants of export intensity within SMEs, a focal point is placed on sustainable development, encompassing the dimensions of environmental, social, and governance (ESG). In their examination, they delineate a spectrum of ESG indicators, comprising elements such as packaging materials recycled and reused and protection of biodiversity as environmental indicators, privacy and data security and human rights as social indicators and audit and control systems and transparency as governance indicators. Noteworthy is their emphasis on the affirmative influence that ESG principles exert on export intensity, with a notable spotlight on the role played by customer demands for certification and adherence to environmental standards (Teplova et al., 2022). Lately, certain authors have undertaken an examination of the influence of ESG performance on SMEs value. The study identified a discernible pattern in the annual escalation of ESG performance among SMEs, alongside an increase in the extent of ESG disclosure. Upon closer examination of performance components, it was discerned that governance performance took precedence, followed by social and environmental performance. The study underscored a substantial and favorable correlation between corporate ESG endeavors and firm value. In light of these constructive findings, the study recommended that managers of SMEs proactively intensify their focus on corporate ESG practices as a strategic approach for fostering long-term business growth and augmenting overall firm value (Narotama et al., 2023).

2.2 Sustainability and innovation determinants and barriers

SMEs emerged as a consequential and dynamic player in the international trade markets. Internally, the possession of essential resources, astute managerial proficiency, and the aptitude to adapt to the dynamic market conditions, as articulated by A. S. Tamer Cavusgil and Gary Knight in their seminal work "Born Global Firms: A New International Enterprise", emerges as a linchpin for SMEs engaged in international trade (Cavusgil & Knight, 2009). Substantive financial resources and adept leadership empower these enterprises to venture into global markets and successfully navigate the complexities of the international economic landscape. Externally, an array of factors, including market growth rate, trade policies, industry feasibility and geopolitical stability, exerts a pivotal influence on the decision-making processes of SMEs (Naveed Hussain & Masood Hussain, 2010). Furthermore, the rapid evolution of technology, notably the proliferation of digital platforms, as highlighted in a study, has played an instrumental role in expanding the global reach of SMEs, streamlining their international operations, and enabling diversification into foreign markets (Cenamor et al., 2019). Moreover, the nuanced comprehension of cultural and societal factors, assumes paramount significance for SMEs, enabling them to adeptly serve foreign markets and establish a competitive edge (Valax & Beddi, 2014). However, the exploration of environmental innovation impact on export performance on SMEs has been rather limited, despite the fact that SMEs make up 99% of all European firms in the European Union and are responsible for approximately 60% of all industrial pollution (Gorgels et al., 2022). Environmental innovation relates to the "creation, adoption, or utilization of a novel product, production process, service, or management/business method within an organization that, throughout its lifecycle, leads to a decrease in environmental risks, pollution, and other adverse effects of resource utilization (including energy usage) when compared to relevant alternatives." (Kemp, 2010). Given their resource constraints, SMEs tend to allocate fewer resources to environmental concerns compared to larger enterprises. Nevertheless, their role in addressing global sustainable development issues is substantial, making them a significant focus of public policies aimed at fostering sustainability.

A comprehensive exploration of the extent of innovation and sustainability in SMEs would remain inconclusive without the inclusion of government policies and support. Scholars investigated the influence of government policies on fostering innovation and sustainability within SMEs across the European Union (Grabowski & Staszewska-Bystrova, 2020). Through a meticulous analysis of diverse data sources, this study illuminates how governmental interventions can mold the landscape of innovation and sustainability for SMEs. The research accentuates the imperative necessity for a facilitative policy environment that encourages active participation of SMEs in sustainable innovation, thereby underscoring the pivotal role played by external factors in shaping the levels of innovation and sustainability within these enterprises.

3. Trade of French SMEs in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region: Status and Characteristics

When discussing SMEs in France, the common perception often gravitates towards the Paris region due to its high concentration of SMEs and micro-enterprises. However, it's essential to recognize the significance of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (ARA) region, which is the focus of this research.

3.1 Status quo of French SMEs in the ARA region

The ARA region stands as a powerhouse in France's industrial landscape, boasting 500,000 jobs distributed across 50,000 sites, thus making it the leading region in terms of industrial employment. The ARA region plays a key role in the country's industrial sector, contributing 18.3% of the region's total value added, a notably higher proportion than the 14.3% found in metropolitan France. This region is also the second most populous in France, home to over 8 million residents, a number that nearly matches the population of Austria and exceeds Denmark's by 40%. Within this expansive region, the urban area of Lyon takes the lead as the most densely populated French metropolis after Paris, housing 2.3 million inhabitants. Remarkably, the ARA region secures its place as France's second-largest region by GDP, surpassing the remarkable milestone of 250 billion euros, contributing 11.6% to the national GDP. On a broader scale, it ranks as the fourth largest region in the European Union and holds the second position within France. Additionally, it boasts the distinction of being the second-largest contributor to the national GDP per inhabitant, amounting to 31,639 euros. Embedded within a thriving economic network, approximately thirty competitiveness clusters lead the charge in pioneering excellence in various domains across the region. In a testament to its robust innovation landscape, ARA, in 2019, housed 14 out of the 56 competitiveness clusters nationally recognized, marking the highest concentration in the country (CCI Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, 2021).

The French government, cognizant of the pivotal role that SMEs play in the nation's GDP and mindful of their recent challenges, has initiated a series of governmental policies and financial support mechanisms for these enterprises. SMEs in the ARA region are among the beneficiaries of these initiatives. The "Plan de Relance," commonly referred to as the "Economic Recovery Plan for France," was instituted in response to the economic exigencies presented by the COVID-19 pandemic. Unveiled in September 2020, this initiative is strategically crafted to invigorate economic convalescence, buttress employment, and advance the shift toward a more sustainable economic paradigm. The French recovery plan boasts a considerable fiscal allocation, featuring substantial investments in various pivotal domains including trade. Within the ARA region, over 16,000 projects have been instituted, representing a cumulative government aid of more than €556.8 billion across all categories (French Government, 2022).

3.2 Characteristics, challenges and determinants of trade of French SMEs in the ARA region

French SMEs operating in the ARA region exhibit a strategic approach to market diversification and export. These businesses understand the importance of expanding beyond domestic boundaries and have implemented various strategies to access global markets. This is particularly evident in this specific region, which borders two foreign nations, Switzerland and Italy. There are a total of 21,192 enterprises currently undertaking export activities (10% of total enterprises in the region). Since SMEs represent 87% of total enterprises in the region it is likely that an important share of the enterprises exporting are SMEs.

SMEs exhibit a higher workforce percentage in the ARA region with 30% compared to the national average 28% (CCI Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, 2021). Notably, sectors such as commerce, transportation, accommodation, catering, and tourism-related activities are disproportionately represented among SMEs, in addition to construction. Despite this, industrial activities, in particular manufacturing, dominate the landscape of SMEs. In Rhône-Alpes, 29% of SME employees are engaged in the manufacturing sector, a trend that aligns with the region's status as the leading industrial hub in France. The pursuit of international trade by SMEs in the ARA region is not without challenges. Due to the recent worldwide events (e.g. Covid-19, wars), inflationary pressures remain. The rising costs remain a major concern, especially the rise in input prices (raw materials, components, service providers, etc.), which affected almost 50% of SMEs in 2023. In addition, rising wages are also a hindrance for almost a quarter of SMEs, a figure that has fallen by a few

points in recent years. However, the major concern for SMEs remains recruitment difficulties (50%) (CCI Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, 2023).

Based on the key figures of the CCI, some possible factors that influence the export activities of French SMEs in the ARA region include: (i) Access to international markets: SMEs may face barriers to entry in foreign markets, such as tariffs, regulations, and cultural differences. The region's support structures, such as ADEME and Pôle Emploi, may aid SMEs in navigating these barriers and identifying export opportunities. (ii) Industry specialization: The region has a diverse economy, with strengths in industries such as manufacturing, technology, and healthcare. SMEs in these industries may have different export opportunities and challenges, depending on the nature of their products and services. (iii) Innovation and competitiveness: SMEs that are able to innovate and offer high-quality, competitive products and services may be more successful in exporting. The region's entrepreneurial culture may contribute to SMEs' ability to innovate and take risks. (iv) Infrastructure and logistics: The region's transportation networks, including highways, railways, and airports, may affect SMEs' ability to export their products and reach international markets.

3.3 Sustainability and innovation within French SMEs in the ARA region

Sustainability and innovation from French SMEs in the ARA region remain largely unexplored and undocumented. As of 2019, the Gross Expenditure on Research and Development (GERD) within the ARA's region investment in research and development (R&D) stands at EUR 7.5 billion, constituting 14% of the national total and 2.7% of the regional GDP, surpassing the national average of 2.2%. Notably, this positions the region as the second-highest contributor to R&D in France. The region hosts 519 companies holding Young Innovative Company status, making up 12.3% of the national total. The region boasts 18.6% of protected inventions in the country, evident in the filing of 2,410 patent applications in 2021. Impressively, 75% of semiconductor patents trace their origins back to this dynamic region. Notably, the region dominates the national landscape in SME patent applications, with six companies securing positions in the Top 10, including the top three (CCI Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, 2023). Government subsidies have been made available to SMEs in recent years to facilitate their sustainability transition (French Government, 2023). Recognizing the crucial role of SMEs and the industrial sector in steering the ecological transition, the French Agency for Ecological Transition (ADEME) has allocated €2.4 billion for this purpose. In the ARA region alone, over 150 companies have reaped the benefits of this support, amounting to almost EUR 37 million in aid (Préfet de la Région Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, 2021). SMEs also have increasingly directed investments towards sustainability (e.g. energy efficiency and lowering emissions intensity). According to the Bpifrance-Rexecode barometer, there is a significant uptick in the percentage of SMEs pinpointing environmental considerations, such as energy savings and waste management, as the driving force behind their investments. Specifically, around 40% of SMEs cited these environmental motives at the end of 2022, 17 percentage points higher than in 2019, showcasing a substantial shift towards sustainable investment practices in recent years. However, disaggregated data on SMEs per region as well as average investments was not available (BPI France, 2023).

4. Methodology: assessing sustainability, innovation and export in the ARA region

This section presents the basic model setting, hypothesis of work, the index system and evaluation indicators.

4.1 Basic model setting

The central question of this study revolves around the potential impact of a synergistic approach to sustainability and innovation on the export performance of French SMEs in the ARA region. The first hypothesis posits that "French SMEs integrating sustainable practices improve their competitive position on the export market." In essence, we expect that SMEs that actively incorporate sustainability into their business operations will gain a competitive advantage in international export markets. The second hypothesis suggests that "Innovation contributes to the ability of French SMEs to adapt to international markets." This hypothesis anticipates that innovation in products and processes is a vital factor enabling French SMEs to effectively adapt and compete in the global export landscape. The third hypothesis states that "A synergistic approach to

sustainability and innovation creates added value in the context of French SME exporters." This hypothesis examines the potential synergies that arise when sustainability initiatives and innovation strategies are combined, and their impact on the overall value generated by French SMEs in export activities.

Many studies analyzing the intricate relationships between innovation, sustainability, and export performance in SMEs employ regression analysis as a fundamental tool to examine the relationships and dependencies. For instance, Villena-Manzanares & Souto-Pérez aimed to analyze the role played by sustainability and innovation on export performance. The study sample covered 180 manufacturing SMEs in Sevilla (Spain) and mobilized a structural equation system using the technique Partial Least Squares (PLS) (Villena-Manzanares & Souto-Pérez, 2016). Similarly, other studies have mobilized various regressions to evaluate innovation, productivity, export and investment climate across manufacturing firms (Véganzonès-Varoudakis & Plane, 2019). The OLS (Ordinary Least Squares) is a method used in regression analysis to estimate the parameters of a linear model by minimizing the sum of squared differences between the observed and predicted values while the 2SLS (Two-Stage Least Squares) is an instrumental variable estimation technique used in econometrics to address endogeneity issues in regression models (Greene, 2018). This study employed OLS and 2SLS regression models to unveil insights into the interplay between sustainability, innovation, and export performance.

The basic regression model is presented as follows:

$$\text{Export Performance} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Sustainability} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Innovation} + \theta_1 \cdot \text{SME characteristics} + \varepsilon$$

In this modified model:

- "Sustainability" represents the level of sustainability practices incorporated by the French SMEs.
- "Innovation" remains the second independent variable, representing the level of innovation employed by the SMEs.
- β_0 is the intercept term.
- β_1 and β_2 are the coefficients associated with the "Sustainability" and "Innovation" variables, respectively, representing their impact on export performance.
- θ_1 are the coefficients associated with the SME characteristics variables.
- ε represents the error term, which captures unexplained variance in the export performance that is not accounted for by the model.

4.2 Developing the Index System

Figure 1. Presentation of the system

Source: Author's elaboration

With regards to the research subject and underlying hypothesis, an index system was proposed (Figure 1).

Sustainability can have a direct effect on export performance and innovation. For instance, sustainability practices can bolster the export performance of SMEs by enhancing their appeal to environmentally conscious international markets (Arora & De, 2020). Innovation can have a direct effect on the two other variables. Innovation in turn can also significantly enhance export performance for SMEs by improving the quality and competitiveness of their products and can be an incentive to export, it is the “self-selection” hypothesis (Cassiman et al., 2010; Lachenmaier & Wößmann, 2006a; Ortigueira-Sánchez et al., 2022). Innovation can also impact sustainability. Sustainability and innovation considered simultaneously can also impact export performance (Bos-Brouwers, 2009; Teplova et al., 2022; Villena-Manzanares & Souto-Pérez, 2016). While not in the scope of our research, sustainability concerns can serve as a motivator for innovation in SMEs, encouraging them to create more eco-friendly products and processes (Bos-Brouwers, 2009) and innovation within SMEs can enhance sustainability by improving resource efficiency and reducing environmental footprints (Kuzma et al., 2020).

While not included in the hypothesis to be tested, it is essential to recognize that export also impacts innovation and sustainability, especially when considering endogeneity. The pursuit of export opportunities can drive SMEs to innovate, as they adapt their products and strategies to meet international market demands, in other words the “learning-by-exporting” hypothesis (Bigsten et al., 2004; Segarra-Blasco et al., 2022). That said, the direction of the impact of exports on innovation (in the broad sense) is uncertain. Exports may provide financial resources or act as an incentive to innovate, in order to preserve or extend their market share. But exporting firms may not be willing to innovate if for example they are dominant in the export market. On the other hand, pursuing international markets can, in turn, encourage SMEs to adopt sustainable practices as they seek to meet the ethical and regulatory requirements of their target markets (Debbarma et al., 2022).

4.3 Evaluation indicators

For being able to respond the specified system, a wide variety of evaluation indicators were mobilized, namely SME characteristics, export-related, innovation-related and sustainability-related.

Regarding SME characteristics, some authors emphasize the age, size (measured by the number of permanent workers), labor productivity (evaluated as value added over employment), and capital intensity (defined as fixed assets over total employment) as key determinants of SME performance (Añón Higón & Drifffield, 2011; D’Angelo et al., 2013). For some authors SMEs affiliated with clusters or belonging to larger groups often benefit from knowledge exchange and resource sharing, which can influence their competitive positioning (Bell et al., 2004). In the context of export orientation and export intensity, the number of enterprises exporting and the percentage of exports in total turnover, or the export-to-turnover ratio, are pivotal indicator (OECD, 2004). Some research recognizes that export intensity can have both positive and negative impacts on SMEs (Haddoud et al., 2021). In terms of sustainability orientation, the number of SMEs recognized as part of a polluting industry offers insights into their environmental impact and potential regulatory risks (Gorgels et al., 2022). Adherence to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) practices, the incorporation of an Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) impact framework, and green product certification (e.g., B-Corp) are indicative of a deeper commitment to sustainable business practices, predictor of enhanced SME competitiveness (Uzhogova et al., 2019). Actions such as waste reduction, energy savings, material recycling, and the use of renewable energy sources can highlight the practical sustainability efforts of SMEs in the region (Gorgels et al., 2022). Then, financial resources allocated to sustainability actions underscore the seriousness and financial commitment of SMEs toward sustainability initiatives (Dobrovolskienė & Tamošiūnienė, 2016). In terms of innovation, the number of SMEs involved in process innovation, product innovation, combined process and product innovation, or non-innovation indicates the level of innovation activity within the SME sector (Szłapka et al., 2017). A patent portfolio, including the number of patents filed in the last three years, can reflect a company's technological and environmental innovation efforts. Innovation investment, represented by R&D expenditure as a percentage of total turnover and the number of training programs on innovation, underscores the financial dedication and human capital investment in innovation processes (Aghmiuni et al., 2020; Lachenmaier & Wößmann, 2006b).

The indicators retained for the specified regression model were collected through a survey questionnaire. The labels and definitions of variables selected are provided in Annex 1.

4.4 Case study application in the ARA region

The ARA region makes a compelling case for assessing sustainability, innovation and export interactions. As reported by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the ARA region, there are a total of 190,380 SMEs located in the region in the year 2023 (CCI Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, 2023a). In order to ensure the study's representativeness, a sample size of 384 SMEs has been calculated, allowing for a 5% margin of error at a 95% confidence level. To gather essential insights, a survey questionnaire with closed and open-ended questions was meticulously crafted and administered to CEOs or managers of SMEs within the region, seeking to gain a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between sustainability, innovation, and their impact on export performance. The survey questionnaire has been carefully designed to capture all the evaluation indicators aforementioned systematically and comprehensively. As of August 2023, a total of 290 survey responses were collected from SMEs, corresponding to a 58% response rate from the total SMEs reached out and 76% of the desired sample size for the current study. In addition to this quantitative analysis, we have also selected a small sample of SMEs to participate in in-depth interviews, providing a qualitative dimension to assess their perspectives on the intricate relationship between sustainability, innovation, and export. For that purpose, an interview guide was prepared.

4.3 Model application procedure

To successfully implement the regression model for the ARA region case study, the following procedure was undertaken. The following steps were established according to the regression model generic procedures proposed by Greene (2018). The steps followed are as follows: (i) Descriptive statistics, (ii) Basic regressions results, (iii) Robustness analysis (generic robustness tests, endogeneity test, heterogeneity test, and heteroskedasticity test), (iv) estimation of regression results.

NB: all costs were calculated in EUR. The computations were all done using STATA.

4.3.1. Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics are specified in Annex 2. Out of the 290 observations, 65% of the SMEs from the sample are from the Manufacturing sector, the average age of operations is estimated at 7 years, the labor productivity and capital intensity at 19.61 and 8.99, respectively, 52% are part of an international group whereas 42% are part of an industrial association cluster, and an average turnover of EUR 391,535. More than half (52%) of the sample has indicated it undertakes export activities, with an average export turnover oscillating around EUR 97,835. Regarding sustainability, more than half of the sample has certifications in place (ISO and green labels), with 52% having a CSR framework in place but only 46% having a ESG framework in place, undertaking on average 4.2 sustainability actions as part of their activities (e.g. minimizing waste, saving materials, reducing CO2 emissions) and investing on average EUR 11,546 in sustainability. Innovation on the other hand, counts a total of 52 innovations, with 77% being process innovations and 67% technological innovations, hence small propensity of product innovations and environmental innovations. From the sample, only 2 SMEs had both product and process environmental innovations. The average R&D expenditure is estimated at EUR 22,227, with only 14 training innovation programs being developed by the SMEs.

4.3.2. Basic regression results

The results of the three regression models are specified in Annex 3. The regression exploring the sustainability impact on export performance (SUS), reveals a change in explanatory power when control variables (age, sector, cluster, group, labor productivity, and capital intensity) are included. Notably, 'CSR' and 'polluting industry' lose statistical significance at the 1% level, while 'certifications' and 'sustainability financing' remain significant, though with altered coefficients. For instance, the effect of sustainability financing shows a decrease in the coefficient compared to the initial model, indicating a nuanced relationship influenced by

control variables. The adjusted R-squared increases to 46%, indicating a better model fit, emphasizing the complexity of the relationship. The regression examining the innovation impact on export performance (INO), shows that with control variables, the model explains approximately 46% of the variance. Significant shifts in the statistical significance and coefficients of independent variables occur. 'R&D expenditure' remains significant at 1%, and 'technological' and 'environmental patents' at 5%, but their coefficients undergo substantial changes. The coefficient for 'environmental patents,' for example, experiences a considerable reduction in magnitude. 'Process innovation' hovers just below the 10% significance level, indicating a new association with a decrease in export turnover. These shifts underscore the impact of control variables on interpreting relationships. The regression exploring the combined impact of sustainability and innovation on export performance with control variables (SUSINO), shows 'certifications,' 'environmental patents,' and 'R&D expenditure' as statistically significant at 5%, while 'sustainability financing' loses significance. Control variables maintain significance, enhancing the model's explanatory power. However, most independent variables show decreased significance and coefficients compared to previous models, highlighting the intricate dynamics influenced by control variables.

4.3.3. Robustness analysis

(i) Basic robustness tests

The model included a wide range of variables related to sustainability, innovation, and control variables. High collinearity between these variables can make it challenging to disentangle their individual effects and can lead to imprecise coefficient estimates. For instance, 'services' and 'productinnov' have been omitted from the model because of collinearity. Robustness tests were carried out on Sectors (Manufacturing, Services, Trade), the Typology of innovation (product or process) and Sustainability (sustainability actions composite indicator). The results of the regressions suggest that it is better to keep only 'manufacturing' since it is the most statistically significant at a significance level of 10% from the considered sectors. Results also showed that with 'product innovation' we lose explanatory power on 'technological patents' and 'environmental patents', whereas this is not the case for 'process innovation'. The robustness test results also suggest that it is preferable to exclude 'sustainability actions' since the adjusted R-squared had a marginal increase and the statistical significance of several independent variables improved, such as 'sustainability financing', 'environmental patents', 'CSR', 'ESG', among others. Another robustness test was performed on the regression model 1 and 2 since it could present an omission variable bias. While the first regression model checks if sustainability impacts export performance it fails to account for the absence of innovation, because it is possible that part of the sustainability explanatory power is explained by innovation, so it is necessary to annulate it to solely focus on the influence of sustainability on export, same holding true for innovation. In the first regression model a non-innovation variable was included and on the second regression model a non-sustainability certification. Both robustness tests indicate that it is better to include them in their respective models to make sure that the results are solely focusing one single component. Several other robustness tests were undertaken by replacing or changing control and explicative variables (including transformations of variables such as exponential or logarithm); however, the outcomes were not very convincing as the model experienced a reduction in explanatory power due to the non-statistically significance of several variables.

(ii) Endogeneity test and instrumental variable

The results of the endogeneity test are specified in Annex 4. The model assumes that the independent variables are exogenous, meaning they are not influenced by the dependent variable ('Export turnover'). However, in reality, some of these variables, especially those related to sustainability and innovation, may be influenced by a SME's export performance, which can lead to endogeneity bias. Assuming that an SME's export performance may influence the amount of "sustainability financing" or "R&D expenditure". For example, higher export performance may lead to increased profitability, which could result in more resources being allocated to sustainability efforts or that SMEs with better export performance may have more resources available for R&D activities. For "sustainability financing", government funding for sustainable initiatives ("GovSfin") and for "R&D expenditure", government R&D grants ("GovRDfin") were considered as instrumental variables (IVs) as they are likely to influence a SME's sustainability financing and R&D

expenditure without influencing its export performance. The correlation results suggest that both endogenous variables have high negative correlation with instrumental variables respectively, hence they are good instruments. This was also confirmed by the Shea Partial R2, Anderson canon p-value, Wald statistic, Anderson-Rubin Wald tests and the Stock-Wright LM S statistic. The low Sargan statistic and the statement "(equation exactly identified)" suggest that the model is exactly identified which means that the number of instruments used is appropriate and does not exceed the number of endogenous variables in the model. This is a desirable outcome because it means that we are not overidentifying the model. Based on the results of the Hausman test, there is no systematic difference in coefficients between the OLS and 2SLS models for the two instrumental variables considered. In other words, there is no evidence of endogeneity in the OLS model. Therefore, we can conclude that the OLS estimates are consistent and unbiased for the coefficients of interest. This result suggests that the OLS model provides valid estimates without the need for 2SLS to address endogeneity concerns in our specific model.

(iii) Heterogeneity test

Different interactions can play an important role in export performance. For instance, an interaction term between "polluting industry" and "environmental audit" may capture whether the impact of environmental audits on export turnover varies for SMEs in polluting industries compared to non-polluting ones. Among the 19 interaction terms computed, only three are statistically significant interaction terms ("sustainability financing and R&D expenditure", "sustainability financing and environmental patents", and "ESG and technological patents"). For example, SMEs that integrate sustainability financing and actively pursue environmental patents are more likely to experience positive outcomes in terms of export turnover. This could imply that environmental innovation, as indicated by the possession of environmental patents, enhances the export performance of SMEs with a financial commitment to sustainability. The other two statistically significant interaction terms lead to a negative impact on export turnover. These results suggest that a synergistic approach to innovation and sustainability is crucial for firms seeking success in export markets, but that not all pathways bring a positive export turnover effect. Firms that strategically integrate sustainability financing and environmental patents are well-positioned to thrive in the competitive landscape of global business. That said, the added complexity with interaction terms does not lead to statistically significant improvements in model fit, therefore these are excluded from the subsequent empirical analysis.

(iv) Heteroskedasticity test

The "Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test" suggested the presence of heteroskedasticity, meaning that the variance of the error terms is not constant. This implies that the assumption of constant error variance is violated, and we need to address or correct for heteroskedasticity in the regression analysis. After considering the transformation of specific variables into logarithm or square root as well as the inclusion of other variables to avoid the omission of variables bias, the heteroskedasticity was still present into our model. To tackle this issue, the heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors was used (also known as White standard errors). This allowed to estimate the coefficients of the three regression models consistently even in the presence of heteroskedasticity. This function has been tested in each of the three-regression models.

4.3.4. Estimation of regression results

The results of the final regressions post-robustness analysis are specified in Annex 5. Under the regression model testing sustainability impact on export performance, having a certification increases export turnover of 27,727 euros under this robust model, which remains consistent with the results obtained by the basic regression model (post-robustness test). Interestingly, "polluting industry" came close to the barrier of 5% to become statistically significant. As such, being in a polluting industry increases the export turnover by 23,086 euros, while non-polluting SMEs would represent a negative influence in export turnover reducing it in the same proportion as the increase. The age, labor productivity, manufacturing sector and the group also remain statistically significant. Under the regression model testing innovation impact on export performance, the basic regression found that 'R&D expenditure' 'technological' and 'environmental patents' were statistically significant at the 5% significance level, while the robust regression only finds 'R&D expenditure' statistically significant at the same level whereas 'technological' and 'environmental patents' at 10% significance level. An additional euro in R&D expenditure brings 1.87 euros more in export turnover, as

found in the basic regression model (post-robustness test). The age and the group are the only ones remaining statistically significant. Under the regression model testing a synergistic consideration of sustainability and innovation impact on export performance, 'certifications,' 'environmental patents,' and 'R&D expenditure' exhibited statistical significance at the 5% level in the basic regression, now in the robust regression only 'certifications' and 'R&D expenditure' remain statistically significant at the same level. Therefore, having an additional euro in R&D expenditure increases export turnover of 1.38 euros while having another unit of sustainability certification increases export turnover by 24,416 euros, both in line with the coefficients found in the basic regression model. Finally, the age, labor productivity and group control variables also remain statistically significant.

5. Empirical findings

This section presents the summary of data analysis results, findings, conclusions and future research recommendations.

5.1 Regression model results

Basic regression models to assess initial relationships, robustness tests to select and adapt the most relevant variables, endogeneity test to ensure that independent variables are exogenous (absence of endogeneity found), heterogeneity test (three interaction terms with statistically significant results), and heteroskedasticity test (presence of heteroskedasticity found) to ensure the validity of regression results have been carried out. The empirical and qualitative evidence supports the hypotheses, emphasizing the positive impact of sustainability integration and innovation adoption for improved export performance. The study highlights the significance of sustainability certifications (EUR24,416 in additional export turnover for every additional certification) and the pivotal role of R&D investment (EUR1.38 boost in export turnover for every additional euro invested in R&D) and environmental patents (EUR64,439 in supplementary export turnover for every additional patent). Qualitative research supplements the findings, offering a richer understanding of the challenges and opportunities facing SMEs implementing sustainability and innovation strategies, especially in terms of environmental footprint reduction.

5.2 Key findings and discussion

Based on the regression model results, it is possible to affirm that a synergistic approach to both sustainability and innovation is the most promising pathway for French SMEs looking to enhance their export prospects. The results indicate that sustainability certifications have a significant positive impact on export turnover, emphasizing the importance of sustainability in international market endeavors. Moreover, research and development (R&D) investment, particularly in environmental innovation, also demonstrates its potential in amplifying export turnover, further underlining the significance of innovation in driving export success. While each pathway individually shows promise, it's the combination of sustainability and innovation that appears to offer the most robust strategy for improving export performance. This approach allows SMEs to leverage the benefits of sustainability certifications and R&D investment, enhancing their competitiveness in international markets. Additionally, considering other factors such as experience, international group affiliations, and careful management of labor productivity and capital intensity ratios can further support the pursuit of increased export prospects. Therefore, a dual focus on sustainability and innovation is recommended for French SMEs, offering a well-rounded strategy to attain improved export prospects and potential sustainable growth in the ARA region.

SMEs, due to their constrained resources, tend to allocate fewer resources to environmental concerns than their larger counterparts, even though they are responsible for more than half of all industrial pollution. SMEs play a pivotal role in the realm of global sustainable development issues and represent a critical target for public policies aiming to foster a sustainable society. They face distinct challenges, stemming from their desire to reduce their environmental footprint, while being limited by their relatively scarce resources. Sustainability and innovation practices provide a good venue for enhanced export performance as well as an

instrument to reduce their environmental footprint. However, the research underscores the complexity of sustainability, which can be both sustainable and unsustainable depending on the contextual dynamics and the prevalence of externalities in any economic activity. It is, therefore, necessary to delve into the intricacies of innovations with respect to sustainability to discern tangible evidence in respect to export performance.

5.3 Conclusion and recommendations

In conclusion, the outcomes have practical implications for French SMEs in the ARA region, guiding them toward a dual focus on sustainability and innovation as a robust strategy for enhancing export prospects. Moreover, the methodological approach, regression models, and systematic steps employed in this study offer a strong basis for future research endeavors seeking to unravel the complexities of sustainability, innovation, and their collective impact on SMEs in regional contexts, possibly under a different research scope, econometric tool, theoretical angle or with additional data.

The empirical results suggest several key policy recommendations to enhance the growth and sustainability of French SMEs. Policymakers should actively support SMEs in obtaining sustainability certifications, offering incentives and educational programs for the certification process. Encouraging increased investment in research and development (R&D) through tax incentives and grants is crucial for innovation and improved export performance. Special emphasis on supporting environmental innovation, possibly through R&D tax credits for environmental technologies, can further boost SMEs' sustainability efforts. Facilitating international affiliations and providing resources for effective labor and capital management are additional avenues for policymakers to enhance SMEs' global competitiveness.

A suggested research topic for the future is: Examining the Impact of Sustainability Practices and Innovation Technologies on the Environmental Footprint and Export Competitiveness of SMEs.

References

- Aghion, P., Bergeaud, A., Lequien, M., & Melitz, M. J. (2018). The Impact of Exports on Innovation: Theory and Evidence [J]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3171084>
- Aghmiuni, S. K., Siyal, S., Wang, Q., & Duan, Y. (2020). Assessment of factors affecting innovation policy in biotechnology [J]. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 5(3), 180–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2019.10.002>
- Añón Higón, D., & Driffield, N. (2011). Exporting and innovation performance: Analysis of the annual Small Business Survey in the UK [J]. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*, 29(1), 4–24. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266242610369742>
- Arora, P., & De, P. (2020). Environmental sustainability practices and exports: The interplay of strategy and institutions in Latin America [J]. *Journal of World Business*, 55(4), 101094. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2020.101094>
- Ayllón, S., & Radicic, D. (2019). Product innovation, process innovation and export propensity: persistence, complementarities and feedback effects in Spanish firms [J]. *Applied Economics*, 51(33), 3650–3664. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2019.1584376>
- Bell, J., Crick, D., & Young, S. (2004). Small Firm Internationalization and Business Strategy [J]. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*, 22(1), 23–56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266242604039479>
- Bigsten, A., Collier, P., Dercon, S., Fafchamps, M., Gauthier, B., Willem Gunning, J., Oduro, A., Oostendorp, R., Pattillo, C., Söderbom, M., Teal, F., & Zeufack, A. (2004). Do African Manufacturing Firms Learn from Exporting? [J]. *Journal of Development Studies*, 40(3), 115–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0022038042000213229>
- Bos-Brouwers, H. E. J. (2009). Corporate sustainability and innovation in SMEs: evidence of themes and activities in practice [J]. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.652>
- BPI France. (2023). *Les investissements verts en hausse chez les TPE et PME françaises*. <https://lelab.bpifrance.fr/enquetes/les-investissements-verts-en-hausse-chez-les-tpc-et-pme-francaises>
- Cassiman, B., Golovko, E., & Martínez-Ros, E. (2010). Innovation, exports and productivity [J]. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, 28(4), 372–376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijindorg.2010.03.005>
- Cavusgil, S. T., & Knight, G. (2009). *Born Global Firms: A New International Enterprise [M]* (Business Expert Press, Ed.).
- CCI Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes. (2021). *Chiffres Clés Auvergne- Rhône-Alpes [R]*. <https://www.auvergne-rhone-alpes.cci.fr/sites/g/files/mwbcuj1546/files/2021-10/Édition%20intégrale%20Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes%20en%20français.pdf>
- CCI Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes. (2023). *Chiffres Clés Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes [R]*.
- Cenamor, J., Parida, V., & Wincent, J. (2019). How entrepreneurial SMEs compete through digital platforms: The roles of digital platform capability, network capability and ambidexterity [J]. *Journal of Business Research*, 100, 196–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.03.035>
- D'Angelo, A., Majocchi, A., Zucchella, A., & Buck, T. (2013). Geographical pathways for SME

- internationalization: insights from an Italian sample [J]. *International Marketing Review*, 30(2), 80–105. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02651331311314538>
- Debbarma, J., Choi, Y., Yang, F., & Lee, H. (2022). Exports as a new paradigm to connect business and information technology for sustainable development [J]. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 7(4), 100233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2022.100233>
- Dobrovolskienė, N., & Tamošiūnienė, R. (2016). Sustainability-Oriented Financial Resource Allocation in a Project Portfolio through Multi-Criteria Decision-Making [J]. *Sustainability*, 8(5), 485. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8050485>
- French Government. (2022). *Plan de Relance [R]*. <https://datavision.economie.gouv.fr/relance-industrie/>
- French Government. (2023). *Dispositifs d'accompagnement à la transition écologique pour les PME industrielles*. <https://www.entreprises.gouv.fr/files/files/secteurs-d-activite/industrie/decarbonation/transition-ecologique-guide-des-aides-pour-les-pme-industrielles.pdf>
- Gaussens, O., & Movahedi, M. (2016). Les effets de l'exportation sur l'innovation et la productivité : le rôle clé de l'apprentissage par l'exportation [J]. *Revue Internationale P.M.E.*, 29(1), 101–141. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1036771ar>
- Golovko, E., & Valentini, G. (2011). Exploring the complementarity between innovation and export for SMEs' growth [J]. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 42(3), 362–380. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jibs.2011.2>
- Gorgels, S., Priem, M., Blagoeva, T., Martinelle, A., & Milanese, G. (2022). *SMEs and environmental sustainability [R]*.
- Grabowski, W., & Staszewska-Bystrova, A. (2020). The Role of Public Support for Innovativeness in SMEs Across European Countries and Sectors of Economic Activity [J]. *Sustainability*, 12(10), 4143. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12104143>
- Greene, W. H. (2018). *Econometric Analysis* (8th ed.). Pearson Education, inc. .
- Haddoud, M. Y., Onjewu, A.-K. E., Nowiński, W., & Jones, P. (2021). The determinants of SMEs' export entry: A systematic review of the literature [J]. *Journal of Business Research*, 125, 262–278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.12.017>
- INSEE. (2018). *Les entreprises en France : Édition 2018 [R]*.
- INSEE. (2020). *Les entreprises en France [R]*.
- INSEE. (2023). *Caractéristiques des entreprises par catégorie en 2021 [R]*. <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/2016091#tableau-figure1>
- Kemp, R. (2010). Eco-innovation: Definition, Measurement and Open Research Issues [J]. *Economia Politica*, 27(3), 397–420.
- Kuzma, E., Padilha, L. S., Sehnem, S., Julkovski, D. J., & Roman, D. J. (2020). The relationship between innovation and sustainability: A meta-analytic study [J]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 259, 120745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120745>
- Lachenmaier, S., & Wößmann, L. (2006a). Does innovation cause exports? Evidence from exogenous innovation impulses and obstacles using German micro data [J]. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 58(2), 317–350. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oepp/gpi043>
- Lachenmaier, S., & Wößmann, L. (2006b). Does innovation cause exports? Evidence from exogenous

- innovation impulses and obstacles using German micro data [J]. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 58(2), 317–350. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oeq/gpi043>
- Love, J. H., & Roper, S. (2015). SME innovation, exporting and growth: A review of existing evidence [J]. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*, 33(1), 28–48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266242614550190>
- Narotama, B., Achsani, N. A., & Santoso, Moch. H. (2023). Corporate Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) and SMEs' Value (a Lesson From Indonesian Public SMEs) [J]. *Indonesian Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship*. <https://doi.org/10.17358/ijbe.9.2.197>
- Naveed Hussain, M., & Masood Hussain, C. (2010). *Factors effecting small and medium enterprises, selection of market entry mode [D]*. BTH School of Management.
- OECD. (2004). *Promoting Entrepreneurship and Innovative SMEs in a Global Economy: Towards a more Responsible and Inclusive Globalisation [R]*.
- OECD. (2018). *Oslo Manual 2018 [M]*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264304604-en>
- Ortigueira-Sánchez, L. C., Welsh, D. H. B., & Stein, W. C. (2022). Innovation drivers for export performance [J]. *Sustainable Technology and Entrepreneurship*, 1(2), 100013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stae.2022.100013>
- Rennings, K., & Rammer, C. (2010). The Impact of Regulation-Driven Environmental Innovation on Innovation Success and Firm Performance [J]. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1692616>
- Segarra-Blasco, A., Teruel, M., & Cattaruzzo, S. (2022). Innovation, productivity and learning induced by export across European manufacturing firms [J]. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 31(5), 387–415. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10438599.2020.1823673>
- Szłapka, J. O., Stachowiak, A., Batz, A., & Fertsch, P. M. (2017). The Level of Innovation in SMEs, the Determinants of Innovation and their Contribution to Development of Value Chains [J]. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 11, 2203–2210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2017.07.367>
- Teplova, T., Sokolova, T., Gubareva, M., & Sukhikh, V. (2022). The Multifaceted Sustainable Development and Export Intensity of Emerging Market Firms under Financial Constraints: The Role of ESG and Innovative Activity [J]. *Complexity*, 2022, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/3295364>
- The World Commission on Environment and Development. (1987). *Our Common Future [M]*.
- UN-DESA. (2020). *Micro-, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises and their role in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals [M]*.
- UNDESA. (2020). *Micro-, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (MSMEs) and their role in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals*. https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/26073MSMEs_and_SDGs.pdf
- Uzhegova, M., Torkkeli, L., & Saarenketo, S. (2019). Corporate Social Responsibility in SMEs: Implications on Competitive Performance Date submitted: October 12, 2017 Revised version accepted after double blind review: December 15, 2018 [J]. *Management Revue*, 30(2–3), 232–267. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0935-9915-2019-2-3-232>
- Valax, M., & Beddi, H. (2014). II. Patricia McDougall et Benjamin Oviatt. L'émergence des entreprises nées globales [M]. In *Les Grands Auteurs en Management International* (pp. 27–47). EMS Editions.

<https://doi.org/10.3917/ems.mayrh.2014.01.0027>

Véganzonès-Varoudakis, M.-A., & Plane, P. (2019). Innovation, exports, productivity and investment climate; a study based on Indian manufacturing firm-level data [J]. *Applied Economics*, 51(41), 4455–4476.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2019.1591606>

Villena-Manzanares, F., & Souto-Pérez, J. E. (2016). Sustainability, innovative orientation and export performance of manufacturing SMEs: An empirical analysis of the mediating role of corporate image [J]. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.3926/jiem.1532>

Annex 1. Variables definition and measurement

Variable Type	Variable	Label	Explanation and significance
Control (characteristics)	Manufacturing	Manuf	SME part of the sector (Yes = 1; No=0)
	Trade	Trd	SME part of the sector (Yes = 1; No=0)
	Services	Serv	SME part of the sector (Yes = 1; No=0)
	Age	Age	Number of years of SME operation (#)
	Size	Size	Number of permanent workers (#)
	Labour productivity	Laprod	Value added over employment (ratio)
	Capital intensity	Capint	Fixed assets over total employment (ratio)
	Turnover	Turnv	Amount of turnover (€)
	Cluster affiliation	Cluster	SME affiliated to a cluster (Yes = 1; No=0)
	Group adherence	Group	SME part of an international group (Yes = 1; No=0)
Explained (export)	Export turnover	Expt	Amount of export turnover (€)
	Export intensity	Exptint	Export turnover over total turnover (ratio)
Explicative (sustainability)	Polluting industry	Pollin	SME in a polluting industry (Yes = 1; No=0)
	Environmental audits	Envaud	SME with environmental audit (Yes = 1; No=0)
	ISO 14001 certification	Iso	SME with ISO 14001 certification (Yes = 1; No=0)
	CSR charter	CSR	SME with CSR charter (Yes = 1; No=0)
	ESG impact framework	ESG	SME with ESG impact framework (Yes = 1; No=0)
	Green product certification	Green	SME with green product certification (Yes = 1; No=0)
	Sustainability actions	Sustact	SME undertaking sustainability actions (# of actions)
	Sustainability financing	Sustfi	SME sustainability financing (€)
Government green subsidies	GovSfin	SME benefitting from government green subsidies (€)	
Explicative (innovation)	Process innovation	Prodinno	Number of SMEs involved in product innovation (#)
	Product innovation	Procinnov	Number of SMEs involved in process innovation (#)
	Total innovation	Tinnov	Total number of process and product innovation (#)
	Technological patent	Techpat	Number of technological patents filed by an SME (#)
	Environmental patent	Envpat	Number of environmental patents filed by an SME (#)
	Total patent	Tpat	Total number of patents filed (#)
	R&D expenditure	RDexp	SME R&D expenditure (€)
	Innovation training programs	Innovpro	Number of training programs (#)
	Government R&D grants	GocRDfin	SME benefitting from government R&D grants (€)

Annex 2. Descriptive statistics framework elements

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Services	290	.093	.291	0	1
Trade	290	.259	.439	0	1
Manufacturing	290	.648	.478	0	1
SMEage	290	7.066	2.916	3	15
SMEsize	290	78.814	65.519	6	224
Valueadd	290	452070.38	145351.83	202493	698484
Labourproductivity	290	19.614	23.179	1.626	152.815
Capitalintensity	290	8.994	10.467	.367	74.567
Totalturnover	290	391535.88	111397.87	200200	599292
Cluster	290	.417	.494	0	1
Group	290	.523	.5	0	1
Exportstatus	290	.524	.5	0	1
Exportturnover	290	97835.848	126977.4	0	393540
Pollutingindustry	290	.548	.499	0	1
Environmentalaudit	290	.517	.501	0	1
Cert	290	1.041	.743	0	2
CSR	290	.517	.501	0	1
ESG	290	.462	.499	0	1
Sustainabilityactions	290	4.193	1.597	0	8
Sustfinancing	290	11545.776	7565.074	1064	29543
Innovation	290	.179	.402	0	2
Productinnov	290	.041	.2	0	1
Processinnov	290	.138	.345	0	1
Totalpatents	290	.179	.402	0	2
Technologicalpatents	290	.121	.326	0	2
Environmentalpatents	290	.059	.263	0	1
RDexpenditure	290	22227.976	18340.059	3009	59208
Innovationprograms	290	.048	.215	0	1

Annex 3. Basic regression results

Variables	(1) SUS	(2) INO	(3) SUSINO
SME age	11175.296*** (1940.967)	11629.689*** (1935.703)	10815.566*** (1922.975)
Labor productivity	-1050.000** (372.959)	-728.626^ (374.735)	-894.133* (374.180)
Capital intensity	1726.331* (823.559)	1815.390* (831.666)	1741.281* (825.567)
Manufacturing	-65047.919** (20709.698)	-41320.134^ (22338.239)	-38834.478^ (21916.646)
Cluster	10590.954 (12124.584)	17748.959 (11995.408)	10489.352 (12045.334)
Group	60337.373*** (13123.325)	49458.761*** (13465.585)	44922.523** (13708.146)
Polluting industry	23804.060^ (12334.052)		14587.334 (12496.913)
Environmental audit	13773.073 (11379.195)		11496.068 (11391.920)
Cert	28345.319*** (8370.893)		24316.302** (8401.516)
CSR	23027.238^ (11715.299)		18828.538 (11816.497)
ESG	-19256.170 (12130.527)		-16059.140 (12077.098)
Sustainability financing	1.931* (0.894)		1.391 (0.901)
Process innovation		-57162.905^ (32816.060)	-40910.645 (32934.136)
Technological patents		70900.355* (31526.760)	48738.852 (31651.631)
Environmental patents		73723.030* (31053.690)	61420.922* (30938.069)
R&D expenditure		1.943*** (0.424)	1.366** (0.444)
Innovation programs		34082.729 (26214.343)	18963.156 (26316.894)
Constant	-47825.964	-42411.814	-72932.692*
N	290	290	290
R2	0.488	0.477	0.512

Annex 4. Final regression results

Variables	(1) SUS	(2) INO	(3) SUSINO
SME age	11230.337*** (1794.550)	11632.438*** (1850.916)	10839.637*** (1755.206)
Labor productivity	-1030.533* (415.757)	-728.301^ (409.952)	-880.841* (399.584)
Capital intensity	1773.199^ (1038.144)	1818.798^ (1042.132)	1772.771^ (1025.229)
Manufacturing	-50377.649** (16533.237)	-40376.673^ (20636.987)	-28973.288 (20303.834)
Cluster	9307.498 (12935.065)	17689.702 (12574.996)	9820.861 (12866.587)
Group	60846.344*** (13643.476)	49499.261*** (14604.897)	44925.026** (13756.861)
Polluting industry	23690.343* (11990.654)		14368.606 (12641.288)
Environmental audit	15027.557 (10853.073)		12212.459 (10904.271)
Cert	28740.458*** (8304.217)		24416.501** (8467.147)
CSR	22883.259^ (12291.688)		18639.041 (12134.791)
ESG	-17109.875 (12043.421)		-14723.629 (11986.953)
Sustainability financing	1.930^ (1.126)		1.370 (1.193)
Process innovation		-57170.934 (41576.640)	-41755.802 (38614.971)
Technological patents		70858.986^ (39914.732)	49309.430 (36676.720)
Environmental patents		73943.301^ (42000.054)	64439.501^ (38645.009)
R&D expenditure		1.943*** (0.532)	1.382* (0.569)
Innovation programs		34194.947 (34846.561)	20818.427 (34386.725)
Constant	-57270.570*	-43413.900	-80250.227**
N	290	290	290
R2	0.485	0.477	0.511